

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRINCIPALS' MANAGEMENT OF INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISION,
PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND TEACHERS' JOB PRODUCTIVITY IN POST BASIC
SCHOOLS IN TARABA STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between principals' management of instructional supervision, performance evaluation and teachers' job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria. The study adopted correlational research design. Three research questions and two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of this study consisted of 5,098 academic staff in 344 post basic schools in Taraba State. The sample was 357 respondents in public post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria; that were selected using multistage sampling technique. An adapted questionnaire, titled "Instructional Supervision and Performance Evaluation Questionnaire (ISPEQ)" and "Teachers' Job Productivity Questionnaire (TJPQ)" respectively were used for data collection. The instrument was validated and trial tested using Cronbach Alpha statistic that gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.766 for ISPEQ and 0.818 for TJPQ. The mean and standard deviation of the obtained data were utilised to answer the study questions, and the hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The research questions result showed that principals' management of instructional supervision and performance evaluation in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria were at moderate levels. The hypotheses findings showed that there was a moderate positive relationship between principals' management of instructional supervision ($r = 0.419, p < 0.05$); performance evaluation ($r = 0.479, p < 0.05$) and teachers' job productivity in the study area. Hence, the researchers came to the conclusion that principals' management of instructional supervision and performance evaluation moderately relates to teachers' job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State. The study recommended among others; that school principals should conduct a collaborative approach to instructional supervision, where feedback is constructive and aimed at improving teaching practices in schools.

Keywords: Instructional Supervision, Performance Evaluation, Teachers' Job Productivity

INTRODUCTION

Education is a fundamental human right that entails the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and routines through diverse forms of instruction, research, and practical experience. Education in general has always been a factory for human development and a source of labour. In reality, the level of education in a nation has a direct impact on the success breakthroughs in technology, economy, social, and political endeavours (Shanka & Adebola, 2021). It is enough to state that human development and educational attainment are strongly correlated, with society's development following. As

all organisations do, the education system needs a variety of resources in order to fulfil its mission. Teachers, often known as human resources, are crucial among these resources. This is because teachers are the ones who are capable of making the other resources (material, machine, money, and market) effective or ineffective (Fwah, 2022). As a result, teachers are essential to achieving the aims and objectives of the institution since the degree of their productivity greatly influences the success of the school.

Productivity, according to Aja-Okorie (2016), is a gauge of how well a given set of resources is applied to meet a given set of objectives. A worker's productivity is a gauge of the extent to which the organization's objectives are met through his dedication to and performance on the job (Nakpodia cited by Fwah, 2022). Employee productivity, according to Mwenda (2013), is the level of production and services that an employee generates in a specific length of time. According to Vipinosa (2015), productivity is the end result of the resources used in conjunction with the efforts made. In the education system, a teacher's job productivity refers to the tasks carried out by a teacher at a specific time in the school system in order to achieve specified goals (Getange, 2016). It may also be referred to as a teacher's capacity to put together pertinent inputs to improve teaching and learning procedures. According to all of these definitions, job productivity can be referred to as nearly any action taken in the direction of achieving a job or goal, which could be high or low depending on the amount of input (i.e., resources) employed by the school. Thus, a key factor in assuring high-quality output is the number of resources employed or engaged during the production process. The information above suggests that resources are essential to teachers' job productivity. However, Ilesanmi, Fadebiyi and Adegoroye (2015) posited that teachers are the principal resource of any school and the effective management of teachers is paramount to achieving school objectives

Asodike, Kaegon, Olawolu and Amadike (2012) described instructional supervision as the use of experts' expertise and experience to monitor, assess, and collaboratively improve the setup and delivery of instructional programmes during the teaching and learning process. Sabitu (2022) stated that instructional supervision includes professional support and direction for teachers and students in order to increase school learning. According to David-West and Kaegon (2017), principals serve as instructional supervisors, by procuring and making materials available for teachers, visiting classes, observe how teachers educate, and manage the class activities. As a supervisor, the principal is responsible for monitoring and reviewing all staff actions and programmes (Nwagwu, 2014). The primary reason for this is to ensure that all personnel are adhering to the law, specified objectives via quality assurance, standard maintenance, and quality control. This viewpoint is supported by the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), which states that supervision is a tool for quality control. As a supervisor, the principal assists teachers in developing their skills in order to improve student learning. The school principal assists instructors in the preparation of lesson plans and notes, the use of instructional methods and teaching aids, the keeping and maintenance of school records, and the management of classrooms (Nwankwoala, 2020; Sabitu, 2022). The principal can provide essential feedback and guidance to teachers in order to boost classroom learning. However, Taraba State principals' instructional supervision must be done with care and consideration for individual teachers' needs and preferences. However, if supervision and performance evaluation processes are not objective, teachers may become demotivated and disengaged from work, thereby affecting their productive level in the study area.

Teachers' performance evaluation, according to Ndungu, Allan and Bomett (2015), refers to the principal's method of evaluating a staff member's value and quality. A key element in improving student learning outcomes is teacher evaluation, sometimes referred to as performance reviews, teacher appraisals, or teacher assessments. Performance evaluation is a process of assessing an employee's job performance and providing feedback on their strengths and weaknesses (Jelagat & Edabu,

2022). Usually, an administrator or supervisor conducts and/or may be involve a formal evaluation process with a set of criteria and performance standards. According to Ndungu et al. (2015), a teacher's evaluation is a determination of the success of a course of action based on how it affects the calibre of the students' learning. According to Okafor (2016), staff evaluation is carried out to help evaluate teachers' performance, which in turn helps evaluate students' academic success. Therefore, an effective teacher assessment system in Taraba State may be a potent instrument for schools, particularly teachers, to improve their instructional practices and become more effective in their roles. Indirectly, this may raise students' academic achievement levels. However, if performance evaluations are conducted poorly or perceived as punitive, they could have a downward influence on teachers' job productivity (Effiong & Ituen, 2022).

In the context of post basic schools in Taraba State, teachers' job productivity hinges on several critical factors, as highlighted by Getange (2016). These include effective teaching practices, meticulous lesson note preparation, adherence to work schedules, diligent supervision, monitoring of students' assignments, and also the will to enforce discipline. Similarly, Orodho, Waweru, and Getange (2014) emphasized that teachers' productivity is significantly shaped by their active involvement in daily school operations, consistent class attendance, fostering student discipline, and the effective use of instructional materials to enhance learning outcomes. Considering how important education is to Taraba State's growth in both society and economy, the contributions of principals and teachers remain indispensable (Getange, 2016). However, challenges in human resource management often pose significant obstacles for school administrators, affecting the achievement of educational goals (Anuolu, 2014). Inefficient instructional supervision and performance evaluation of teachers by principals, such as poor utilization of teaching staff, could adversely impact staff effectiveness and, ultimately, students' academic performance. These issues indicate the need for strategic leadership and effective staff supervision and evaluation in Taraba State's post basic schools to enhance productivity and achieve educational objectives. Nevertheless, there is a lack of empirical data in this study area to support this assertion or any that the researcher is privy of. In light of this, the researcher sought to investigate whether there is a connection between principals' instructional supervision, performance evaluation and teachers' job productivity by using post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In an ideal school environment, an effective teacher's job productivity should be reflected by effective classroom management, high student academic achievement, effective lesson preparation and delivery, teachers' continuous improvement, and positive relationships with students and colleagues. As observed by the researcher, the current state of teachers' job productivity most public senior secondary schools in Nigeria and Taraba state particularly stems from low teaching performance, lack of teaching resources and materials, and infrastructural equipment. This has led to poor working conditions, excessive workloads for teachers, high student-to-teacher ratios, insufficient teacher training and development, low teacher morale and motivation, and teacher turnover in most Taraba State post basic schools.

Despite this, Nigeria's educational system has a number of problems. The most notable is teachers' low productivity (Effiong & Ituen, 2022; Fwah, 2022), which may be correlated with low students' academic achievement, disruptive student conduct, and a decline in educational quality, among others. Also, the researcher observed a prevalent trend among Nigerians wherein they exhibit reluctance in enrolling their children in public senior secondary schools, because some of these students may struggle with reading and writing, examination fraud, truancy, bullying, extortion, and other social vices. This has further prompted stakeholders' concerns regarding the productivity of public senior secondary school teachers. In addition, there are reports of senior secondary school teachers in public schools within the state, particularly in rural areas, exhibiting poor work

behaviours such as sitting under the trees and not in class, going to class few minutes before their class period is over, and preferring to sell goods in the class.

Consequential, teachers' job productivity continues to decline, as some teachers become demoralised mostly due to poor basic amenities for performing their jobs. This has further contributed to teachers' lack of enthusiasm, attention, and continuity in their work, as the researcher has observed. There is no doubt that these vices when left unattended could make teachers experience frustration, lose motivation, and become less effective at their jobs. However, there is dearth of empirical evidence to back up these claims and the role played by principals' instructional supervision and performance evaluation in post basic schools in Taraba State, which has created a gap that the current study seeks to fill. In light of this, the researchers designed this study to investigate the relationship between principals' instructional supervision, performance evaluation and teachers' job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between principals' instructional supervision, performance evaluation and teachers' job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of this study were to determine the:

1. Relationship between principals' management of instructional supervision and teachers' job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria.
2. Relationship between principals' management of performance evaluation and teachers' job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the level of principals' management of instructional supervision in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of principals' management of teachers' performance in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of teachers' job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between principals' management of instructional supervision and teachers' job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria.
- Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between principals' management of performance evaluation and teachers' job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical framework of this study is anchored on Penrose's (1959) Resource Based Theory. Resource-Based Theory was propounded by Edith Penrose in 1959 through her influential book titled "The Theory of the Growth of the Firm" in 1959, which laid the foundation for the Resource-Based Theory. The theory states that resources and capabilities possessed by a firm are crucial determinants of its ability to grow and compete in the market (Penrose, 1959). The RBV theory is a management theory that focuses on the internal resources and organisational capabilities of a firm as key drivers of

competitive advantage. The RBV underscores the importance of organizational capabilities, including HRM capabilities. Principals who demonstrate dynamic capabilities in adapting HRM practices to evolving educational landscapes, technological advancements, and changing student demographics are better positioned to enhance teachers' job productivity over time. This adaptability might involve adjusting professional development strategies, implementing flexible work arrangements, or leveraging technology to support teaching practices.

Instructional Supervision and Teachers' Job Productivity

According to Obasi (2009), supervision refers to energising, directing, improving, renewing, encouraging, and overseeing a group with the objective of ensuring the group's participation so that the supervisors can carry out their duty successfully. Helping teachers enhance their teaching methods, boost their efficacy in the classroom, and eventually enhance student learning outcomes is the aim of instructional supervision. Elenwo (2018) investigated the relationship between secondary school pupils' academic achievement in Rivers State, Nigeria, and the supervision provided by their principals. The study found that students' performance on the senior secondary certificate exam is significantly influenced by the principals' evaluations of teachers, their observations of instructors in the classroom, and the teachers' adherence to the work plan. Additionally, Yousaf, Bushra, and Talat (2018) looked into how school principals' supervision practices affected the productivity and development of teachers in Pakistani society. The results, obtained from correlation and regression analyses, revealed that supervision practices of principals related to teachers' development are indeed helpful in attaining better performance of teachers and their overall growth.

Performance Evaluation and Teachers' Job Productivity

The practice of evaluating an employee's work performance and giving them comments on their strengths and shortcomings is known as performance evaluation (Jelagat & Edabu, 2022). Effiong and Ituen (2022) aimed to ascertain the connection between the job productivity of Business Studies instructors in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom South Education Zone, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, and performance appraisal techniques. The study's conclusions showed that the job productivity of business studies teachers in public secondary schools in the Akwa Ibom South Education zone is strongly and significantly correlated with their use of management by objectives, 360-degree feedback, and assessment centre appraisal strategy. The impact of monitoring and evaluation on efficient teaching and learning in secondary schools in Kenya's Githunguri area was examined by Ndungu, Allan, and Bomett (2015). The study's conclusions offered crucial insight into how principals' oversight and assessment of effective teaching and learning in secondary schools works.

METHODOLOGY

The data for this study was gathered using a correlational research design. Taraba State was the study's location. 5,098 academic staff members which included 4,754 teachers and 344 school principals from post-basic schools in Taraba State made up the study's population. 357 academic staff members (24 administrators and 333 teachers) from 24 public post-basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria, made up the study's sample. The multistage sampling technique was used to pick the sample size, which was then calculated using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula. Data was gathered using a self-developed and modified questionnaire called the Teachers' Job Productivity Questionnaire (TJPQ) and the Instructional Supervision and Performance Evaluation Questionnaire (ISPEQ), respectively.

The two instruments were however designed using a Likert response like scale that ranges from 1 to 5, with 5 representing the highest and 1 representing the lowest scale. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity, which was done by three experts and trial tested using Cronbach's Alpha statistic that gave reliability co-efficient of 0.766 for ISPEQ

and 0.818 for TJPQ. The data was collected within three weeks with the services of three research assistants and later analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions; while PPMC was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The results are presented in the order of research questions 1 – 3 and hypotheses 1 – 2 from table 1 to table 5. For the research questions, the keys represent: n = no of respondents; and Std. Dev = Standard Deviation.

Research Question 1: What is the level of principals’ management of instructional supervision in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of Principals’ Management of Instructional Supervision in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	n = 339	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	My school principal vets my lesson plans to ensure quality of standard		3.78	1.48	High Level
2.	My school principal visits my classes during lesson periods		3.04	1.34	Moderate Level
3.	My school principal inspects my students’ notes to ensure scheme coverage.		3.58	1.35	High Level
4.	My school principal uses teachers’ competency to rate teachers’ input		2.47	1.44	Low Level
5.	My school principal employs clinical supervision to help me improve my teaching skills.		3.23	1.32	Moderate Level
6.	My principal always gives feedback after his supervision		3.63	1.40	High Level
	Grand Mean		3.29	1.39	Moderate Level

Table 1 shows the responses of the respondents to research question 1. The table reveals that items 1, 2 and 6 were at a high level in post basic schools in Taraba State; while items 2 and 5 were at a moderate level, and also item 4 was at a low level. The table further reveals a grand mean response score of 3.29 and standard deviation of 1.39. This finding implies that principals’ management of instructional supervision in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria is at a moderate level.

Research Question 2: What is the level of principals’ management of teachers’ performance evaluation in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of Principals’ Management of Teachers’ Performance Evaluation in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	n = 339	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
7.	My school principal is unbiased during teachers’ evaluation		3.67	1.19	High Level
8.	My principal evaluates my teaching efficacy		3.47	1.35	Moderate Level
9.	My school principal applied key performance indicators (KPI) for evaluation purpose		3.34	1.19	Moderate Level
10.	My principal uses one method of rating teachers’ performance		2.30	1.52	Low Level

11. My principal uses task performance as a means of recommending staff for promotion	3.99	1.08	High Level
12. My principal gives feedback after evaluating teachers in the school	4.04	1.23	High Level
Grand Mean	3.47	1.26	Moderate Level

Table 2 shows the responses of the respondents to research question 2. The table reveals that most of the items 7, 11 and 12 were at high level in post basic schools in Taraba State; while item 8 and 9 were at a moderate level and also item 10 was at a low level. The table further reveals a grand mean response score of 3.47 and standard deviation of 1.26. This finding implies that principals’ management of teachers’ performance evaluation in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria is at a moderate level.

Research Question 3: What is the level of teachers’ job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of Teachers’ Job Productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	n = 339	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	Participation in curricular activities in school		3.68	1.34	High Level
2.	Participation in extracurricular activities in school		3.63	1.36	High Level
3.	Improvisation of instructional material		3.58	1.34	High Level
4.	Overseeing students’ classroom behaviour		3.67	1.27	High Level
5.	Involving students in routine class tasks		3.68	1.25	High Level
6.	Keeping proper students’ records		3.59	1.31	High Level
7.	Involvement in decision-making		4.16	0.87	High Level
8.	Updating of knowledge		3.64	1.31	High Level
9.	Supporting students’ reading development		3.91	1.12	High Level
10.	Contribution to the school’s goals and objectives		3.87	1.17	High Level
11.	Enhancing the welfare of students in the classroom		3.53	1.34	High Level
12.	Raising students’ writing proficiency		3.86	1.22	High Level
13.	Relationships with the host community		3.60	1.44	High Level
14.	Relationships with co-workers		3.83	1.22	High Level
15.	Relationships with parents		4.06	0.87	High Level
16.	Relationships with principals		3.34	1.43	Moderate Level
17.	Student discipline		2.83	1.57	Moderate Level
18.	Capacity to take initiative		2.77	1.62	Moderate Level
19.	Improvement of students’ behaviour in the school		3.68	1.22	High Level
20.	Increase in students’ passing rates		3.75	1.22	High Level
21.	Evaluation of students		3.72	1.51	High Level
22.	Advising students		3.67	1.28	High Level
23.	Improving students’ self-confidence		3.86	1.16	High Level
24.	Getting to school on time		3.86	1.09	High Level
25.	Constructive contribution during staff meetings		3.62	1.28	High Level
Grand Mean			3.66	1.27	High Level

Table 3 show the responses of the respondents to research question 3. The table reveals that items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24 and 25 were at high level in post basic schools in Taraba State; while items 16, 17 and 18 which were at moderate level. The table further reveals a grand mean response score of 3.66 and standard deviation of 1.27. This finding means that teachers’ job productivity level in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria is at a high level.

Hypotheses Testing

The hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) for testing hypotheses 1 – 2 at a significance level of 0.05. Hence, the following acronym stands as; N = number of respondents; X = Mean; S.D = Standard Deviation; sig = level of significance, and *r* = Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The findings are as follows:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between principals’ management of instructional supervision and teachers’ job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis on Principals’ Management of Instructional Supervision and Teachers’ Job Productivity

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	<i>r</i>	p-value	Decision
Instructional Supervision	339	3.29	1.39	0.419	0.000	Reject
Teachers’ Job Productivity	339	3.66	1.27			

Significant (p<0.05) (2-tailed)

Table 4 indicates Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis conducted on the relationship between principals’ management of instructional supervision and teachers’ job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State. The result shows that there is a positive relationship between principals’ management of instructional supervision and teachers’ job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, thus hypothesis 1 is rejected as *r* = 0.419, *n* = 339, when *p* < 0.05.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between principals’ management of performance evaluation and teachers’ job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis on Principals’ Management of Performance Evaluation and Teachers’ Job Productivity

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	<i>r</i>	p-value	Decision
Performance Evaluation	339	3.47	1.26	0.479	0.000	Reject
Teachers’ Job Productivity	339	3.66	1.27			

Significant (p<0.05) (2-tailed)

Table 5 indicates Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis conducted on the relationship between principals’ management of performance evaluation and teachers’ job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State. The result shows that there is a positive relationship between principals’ management of performance evaluation and teachers’ job productivity in post basic schools in Taraba State, thus hypothesis 2 is rejected as *r* = 0.479, *n* = 339, when *p* < 0.05.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

With a grand mean score of 3.29, the study concluded that principals in post-basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria, manage instructional supervision at a moderate level. A reasonable degree of instructional monitoring indicates that principals are assisting instructors to a certain extent without becoming unduly involved. This can achieve a balance between guaranteeing responsibility and giving educators the freedom to experiment and modify their pedagogical approaches. This result was in line with research by Kieleko, Kanori, and Mugambi (2017), Iroegbu and Etudor-Eyo (2016), and Sule (2013) that showed that instructional supervision was important and helped teachers in their careers in terms of syllabus coverage, professional growth, and process enhancement. However, the results conflict with those of a study by Elenwo (2018) that indicated that secondary school principals had little instructional monitoring. This study implies that a culture of cooperation and open communication between principals and teachers can be fostered by modest supervision. Teachers could feel more at ease asking for advice and offering suggestions for development in post basic schools in Taraba State.

Additionally, hypothesis 1 was disproved because the data indicated a moderately favourable association ($r = 0.419$, $n = 339$, when $p < 0.05$) between the job productivity of instructors and the way principals conduct instructional supervision in Taraba State's post-basic schools. There appears to be a somewhat favourable linear association between instructors' job productivity and the way principals handle instructional supervision, according to the positive correlation coefficient ($r = 0.419$). The results are consistent with those of Fwah (2022), who found a strong positive correlation between the job productivity of teachers in senior secondary schools in Adamawa State and the instructional supervision provided by principals. ($p < 0.05$, $r = 0.80$). It did not, however, concur with Elenwo's (2018) conclusion that there is no meaningful connection between students' performance in S.S.C.E. and the principals' observations of teachers in the classroom or their adherence to the work plan. This research suggests that by managing instructional supervision, principals in Taraba State's post-basic schools have the ability to affect and improve teachers' job productivity. Principals may use techniques including giving insightful criticism, observing classes, and establishing specific learning objectives during instructional supervision.

With a grand mean score of 3.47, the study concluded that principals in Taraba State, Nigeria's post-basic schools manage teacher performance evaluations at a reasonable level. This result supported the findings of Effiong and Ituen (2022), Mbabu, Kirimi, and Nyambura (2022), Türkoğlu and Aypay (2022), Ndungu et al. (2015), and Kadenyi (2014) that school heads moderately do performance reviews in secondary schools. According to a study by Türkoğlu and Aypay (2022), instructors received awards both during the year and at the end of the year based on the outcomes of their performance reviews. This conclusion implies that a moderate amount of performance evaluation indicates that principals are administering evaluations that are neither overly forgiving nor very harsh. As a result, teachers' strengths and areas for development may be more fairly and accurately represented.

Additionally, hypothesis 2 was rejected because the data indicated a moderately good link ($r = 0.479$, $n = 339$, when $p < 0.05$) between the job productivity of teachers and the way principals conduct performance evaluation in Taraba State's post-basic schools. The positive correlation value ($r = 0.479$) indicates that the productivity of teachers on the job and the way principals handle performance reviews have a somewhat favourable linear relationship. The results were consistent with those of Effiong and Ituen (2022), who found a strong and significant correlation between the job productivity of Business Studies teachers in Public Secondary Schools in the Akwa Ibom South Education zone and their use of management by objectives, 360-degree feedback, and assessment centre appraisal strategy. The results also concur with those of Fwah (2022), who found a strong positive correlation between the job productivity of teachers in senior secondary schools in Adamawa State and the

instructional supervision provided by principals. ($p < 0.05$, $r = 0.80$). The findings suggest that by managing performance evaluation, principals in Taraba State's post-basic schools have the ability to affect and improve teachers' job productivity. This could entail tactics like offering support for progress, establishing clear performance goals, and giving constructive criticism.

With a grand mean score of 3.66, the study concluded that instructors in post-basic institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria, are highly productive at their jobs. The average productivity of instructors in Taraba State's post-basic schools is high, as indicated by their grand mean score of 3.66. This is a favourable evaluation of their efforts and commitment to their positions. Providing high-quality education is frequently linked to high teacher productivity. It shows that educators are doing their jobs well and making a positive impact on students' entire educational experiences. This finding implies that high teacher productivity can positively affect student outcomes, such as academic success and personal growth. Teachers that are productive are more likely to inspire success, engage students, and establish productive learning environments. Schools may attract more skilled teachers if they have a reputation for having high teacher productivity. It can aid in luring and keeping outstanding educators, which can raise the standard of education even further.

CONCLUSION

The study's conclusions provide insight into the connection between the productivity of teachers in Taraba State's post-basic schools and the way the principal oversees performance reviews and instructional supervision. These characteristics and instructors' job productivity were shown to be moderately but significantly correlated by the study. The study came to the conclusion that instructors' job productivity in Taraba State's post-basic schools is somewhat correlated with the way principals oversee instructional monitoring and performance evaluation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In addition, based on the findings of the study, the study recommends the following:

1. School principals are also encouraged to conduct a collaborative approach to instructional supervision, where feedback is constructive and aimed at improving teaching practices.
2. School authorities are encouraged to review and update their performance evaluation processes in order to ensure they are fair, transparent, and aligned with educational goals.
3. The government through the Post Basic School Board should allocate resources to support the teacher's job in senior secondary schools, including funding for staff professional development, technology integration, and performance evaluation tools.

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